

LEXICAL AND GRAMMATICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF VERBAL METAPHORS IN PROVERBS AND SAYINGS

Sh.Saymanova

Doctoral Student, Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18081592>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 25th December 2025

Accepted: 26th December 2025

Online: 27th December 2025

KEYWORDS

“Among Tokhtamysh Khan’s people, I had one fragment, He was a camel who traveled the world, He was a hero surpassing heroes

ABSTRACT

Metaphor primarily exerts a direct influence on mental imagery: it is perceived, created in a distinctive manner, and articulated. The addressee derives meaning from the perceived image. Thus, metaphor allows the addressee to transfer interpretation from one semantic meaning to another

Metaphor primarily exerts a direct influence on mental imagery: it is perceived, created in a distinctive manner, and articulated. The addressee derives meaning from the perceived image. Thus, metaphor allows the addressee to transfer interpretation from one semantic meaning to another.

Metaphors derived from verbs, like nominal metaphors, occupy a significant place in the structure of proverbs and sayings. Often, nominal words combine with auxiliary verbs such as *edim* (was), *edi* (was), *boldım* (became), and others, forming sequences of verbal metaphors. However, proverbs formed with auxiliary verbs are relatively few and are more frequently encountered in epic narratives. For example, the following metaphors are used: *Toqtamis xanniń xalqında, Bir sınarım bar edi, Dúnyanı gezgen nar edi, Erden asqan er edi, Dúnyanı gezgen sher edi, Atam meniń námálim, Tuwǵan anam peri edi.*

Translated:

“Among Tokhtamysh Khan’s people, I had one fragment, He was a camel who traveled the world, He was a hero surpassing heroes, He was a lion who roamed the world, My father was unknown, My mother was a fairy”.

Júk kótergen qatarında nar edi,

Panayıma bir neshsheler zar edi.

“He was a camel among those who bore heavy loads,

Many were in need of my protection.”

In these examples, the word “**nar**” refers to a specific type of camel; however, through its literal associations with strength, endurance, and physical stature, human qualities are metaphorically depicted. The word “**sher**” in the literary language is a doublet of “**jolbarıs**” (“tiger”). In this example, the characteristics of this predatory animal are metaphorically transferred and implied. The word “**peri**” (fairy), by contrast, denotes an abstract concept, and its figurative meaning predominates over its literal meaning.

Example: Baǵımnıń gúli solǵalı, Aqılımdı dushpan alǵalı, Otız eki kún tolǵanı, Ashıldı baǵda gúlzarım, Óter dushpannan arıń, Gá jarılqa, gá ǵarǵa, Sol dur sizge aytarım.

Translated:

“The flower of my fortune has withered,
The enemy has taken my wisdom,
When thirty-two days had passed,
My flower garden bloomed in the yard.
Escape from the passing enemy,
Whether blessed or cursed,
This is what I say to you.”

In the expressions “**the withering of the flower,**” “**the enemy taking wisdom,**” and “**the blooming of the flower garden,**” human actions and states are represented figuratively. Through metaphors associated with “**flower**” and “**flower garden**”, similarities between natural changes and phenomena and human conditions and actions are emphasized.

In proverbs and sayings, action-denoting words often function metaphorically. In such cases, they depart from their literal meanings and, when used figuratively, are associated with human qualities and states, serving expressive and aesthetic purposes. Examples include: Qalıń jurttı jamanlama, Jurtshılıq tabar minińdi, Eki ushlı sóz aytsań, Qızarlatadı júzińdi; - (Do not speak ill of the whole people, the community will find your fault. If you utter a double-edged word, it will redden your face). Kórpeniń juqası tońdırar, Kewil juqası azdırar; - (A thin quilt makes one cold; a shallow heart leads one astray). Ómir sawdası oyın emes; - (Life's trade is not a game) Adam ólse de, úmit ólmes; - (A person may die, but hope does not). Sózdiń bası bir pushpaq, Ayaǵı boldı qırpishpaq; - (The beginning of a word is a corner; its end becomes a cliff). Jigittiń tóresi bolsa, Sóziniń shiresi bolar; - (If a man is noble, his word will be firm). Erdiń sáni el bolar, Eldiń sáni jer bolar, Jerdiń sáni suw bolar; - (The worth of a hero is his people; the worth of the people is their land; the worth of the land is water). Kózi kórmes, kewil kórer; - (The eye may not see, but the heart sees). Bolmas iske polat bol, Polattan da qattı bol; - (Be steel in an impossible task; be harder than steel). Haqıyqatlıq mayıssa da, sınbaydı; - (Truth may bend, but it does not break).

Comparable metaphorical constructions are also found in English proverbs, such as: **A rolling stone gathers no moss; Actions speak louder than words; Don't count your chickens before they're hatched; You can't have your cake and eat it too; Bite the bullet; Cutting corners; Don't put all your eggs in one basket.**

The phrase “**a rolling stone**” (a nominal construction) depicts the continuous movement of a stone and functions as a metaphor for activity, constant motion, and the absence of permanence. The phrase “**gathers no moss**” (a verbal construction) metaphorically represents problems, burdens, or negative consequences. Moss typically grows on stationary and undisturbed surfaces.

The proverb employs a simple Subject–Verb–Object structure to convey metaphorical characterization. The metaphor suggests that a person who continues to act, change, or learn avoids the accumulation of unfavorable consequences or burdens (symbolized by moss). Overall, the proverb promotes adaptability, openness to change, and the rejection of stagnation.

The primary function of proverbs and sayings in the native language is to encourage unity and harmony among members of society, regardless of social class. They cultivate loyalty to the homeland and ancestral land, promote reconciliation and cooperation, and emphasize the importance of mastering a profession or craft.

Metaphors in proverbs serve to convey ideas clearly and precisely. Within the corpus of folk wisdom, metaphors express didactic thoughts and moral teachings in a concise and artistic manner. Proverbs often employ metaphor and other stylistic devices to communicate complex and structured ideas in a compact form. Many proverbs carry dual meanings, in which ordinary words acquire deep symbolic significance. The lexical composition of proverbs is minimal, yet they convey diverse and multilayered conceptual content. From a functional perspective, proverbs hold notable practical and social importance.

References:

1. Арутюнова Н. Д. Метафора и дискурс // Теория метафоры: сборник: пер. с англ., фр., нем., исп., польск. яз. / вступ. ст. и сост. Н.Д. Арутюновой; Общ. ред. Н.Д. Арутюновой и М.А. Журиной. — М.: Прогресс, 1990. — с. 5—31. (Arutyunova, N. D. (1990). Metaphor and discourse. In N. D. Arutyunova & M. A. Zhurinskaya (Eds.), Theory of metaphor (pp. 5–31). Moscow: Progress. Original work in Russian; translations from English, French, German, Spanish, Polish.)
2. Қарақалпақ фольклоры, 88–100 томлар. Нөкіс: «Илим», 2015. (Karakalpak Folklore, Vols. 88–100. Nukus: Ilim, 2015.)
3. Speake, J. (2015). Oxford Dictionary of Proverbs. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
4. Proverbicals. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://proverbicals.com>